

Study on Effective Adsorbent of Waste Writing Papers for the Removal of Methylene Blue

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Abstract

Waste writing paper samples were collected from some used practical record books from chemistry laboratories, Department of Chemistry, Bago University. Waste writing papers were deinked by using hydrogen peroxide and sodium lauryl sulphate and then treated with 5% NaOH. The resultant samples were coded as untreated waste writing papers (UWP) and NaOH treated waste writing papers (TWP). The physicochemical properties of UWP and TWP (moisture, ash, PH) were determined by conventional methods. The corresponding functional groups and surface morphologies of samples were characterized by FTIR and SEM analyses. A batch adsorption study was conducted under various initial concentration of methylene blue and adsorbent dosage. Removal percent of methylene blue on TWP (64.514%) was higher than that of UWP (41.106%) at optimum conditions. From this investigation, it was observed that TWP is more efficient adsorbent than UWP. Therefore, TWP can be used as effective adsorbent for the removal of methylene blue.

Keywords : Untreated waste writing papers, NaOH treated waste writing papers, adsorption, methylene blue

Introduction

One of the most important industrial pollutants, especially in textile industries, is the dyes that even at low concentrations of one parts per million (ppm) are recognizable by naked eyes. It is also estimated that about 10% of the produced dyes are annually entered into the environment, which causes problems for both humans and the wild life. One of the mostly consumed materials in the dye industry is Methylene Blue (MB) which is used for cotton and silk dyeing. Up to now, a great number of methods have been proposed in order to remove dyes from the industrial waste water, among which adsorption is the most acceptable due to its cost effectiveness and the possibility of usage in large scales (Baghapour, *et. al*, 2013).

When a solid surface is exposed to a gas or a liquid, molecules from the gas or the solution phase accumulate or concentrate at the surface. The phenomenon of concentration at the molecules of a gas or liquid at a solid surface is called adsorption. "Adsorption" is a well established and powerful technique for treating domestic and industrial effluents.

Waste paper is one of the main components of urban waste. About 6.43 % of the municipal solid waste in urban were waste papers and card board (Ahmad, *et. al*, 2009). In this study, the waste writing papers were treated with NaOH and characterized. The removal of methylene blue from aqueous dye solution was investigated by the prepared waste writing papers as adsorbent.

Materials and Methods

Preparation of Sample

The waste writing papers collected from Department of Chemistry, Bago University were deinked by hydrogen peroxide and sodium lauryl sulphate. The untreated waste writing papers (UWP) were obtained. Some of the deinked samples were mixed with 5% sodium hydroxide and refluxed 95°C for 4h. The resultant sample was washed several times with distilled water until pH is about 7. The sample was dried at 105°C and stored in sealed bottle and coded as NaOH treated waste writing papers (TWP).

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Characterization of Untreated and NaOH Treated Waste Writing Papers

The moisture contents and ash contents of UWP and TWP were determined by AOAC method. pH of the samples were determined by pH meter. FTIR spectra for UWP and TWP were recorded by using Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrometer (FTIR 8400, Shimadzu, Japan). UWP and TWP were examined by scanning electron microscope (SEM) for a visual inspection of external porosity and micro - texture. The SEM model is Jeol - JSM - 5610.

Adsorption Studies of Untreated and NaOH Treated Waste Writing Paper Samples

Maximum adsorption wavelength for methylene blue dye solution was determined by using the spectrophotometer. At this maximum adsorption wavelength, calibration curve was constructed by absorbance Vs various dye concentrations. Adsorption studies on UWP and TWP for the removal of methylene blue were carried out by the different parameters (20 to 100mgL⁻¹ of initial dye concentrations and 0.2 to 1g of adsorbent dosage). The removal percents of methylene blue were determined at optimum conditions of adsorption parameters.

Results and Discussion

Physicochemical Properties of Untreated Waste Writing Papers (UWP) and NaOH Treated Waste Writing Papers (TWP)

It was found that TWP has higher moisture and ash content than that of UWP. It is probable that treated adsorbent being the separated long fibers may have the ability to take up more moisture. The pH value of NaOH treated waste writing papers (TWP) indicates the basic characteristic of adsorbent. Figure 1 and 2 showed the FTIR spectra of UWP and TWP. The bands around 1650 - 1300 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ring vibration in a large aromatic skeleton generally found in cellulosic material. The FTIR spectra showed a characteristic cellulose peak in the region of 1000 to 1200 cm⁻¹. SEM micrographs of UWP and TWP are presented in Figures 3 and 4 respectively. It was obvious that untreated waste writing papers (UWP) and NaOH treated waste writing papers (TWP) showed the different morphologies. It can be seen that the surface of UWP has small fibrous substances. After treating, the surface of TWP showed the pit structure of separated fibers.

Figure(1) FTIR spectrum of untreated waste writing papers (UWP)

Figure(2) FTIR spectrum of NaOH treated waste writing papers (TWP)

Figure (3) Scanning electron micrograph of untreated waste writing paper

Figure (4) Scanning electron micrograph of NaOH treated waste writing paper

Removal of Dyes by Untreated Waste Writing Papers (UWP) and NaOH Treated Waste Writing Papers (TWP)

The results for the removal of methylene blue by UWP and TWP are shown in Table 1, 2, 3 and 4 respectively. As the data clearly show that removal percent of methylene blue by TWP was considerably higher than that of UWP, especially, at higher initial concentration of dye. It indicated that the removal percent of methylene blue increases continuously from 56.92 to 90.00 % with an increase adsorbent dosage and then nearly equilibrium condition was observed. According to these data, 0.4g was taken as the suitable adsorbent dosage for UWP. Adsorption percent of TWP increases significantly around 0.4g and there are increased slowly. The adsorbent dosage of 0.4g was chosen for optimum dosage. It indicated that the removal percent of methylene blue by UWP and TWP were found to be 41.106% and 61.514% respectively at optimum condition. This suggests that NaOH treated waste writing papers (TWP) was effective adsorbent for the sorption of methylene blue compared to untreated waste writing papers (UWP).

Table(1) Effect of Initial Methylene Blue Concentration on the Removal of Methylene Blue by Untreated Waste Writing Papers

Initial concentration Methylene Blue (ppm)	Final concentration (ppm)	Removal percent (%)
20	11.779	41.106
40	25.962	35.096
60	45.087	24.856
80	61.490	23.137
100	79.692	20.308

UWP = Untreated Waste Writing Papers, Dosage =0.4 g / 50mL

Table (2) Effect of Initial Methylene Blue Concentration on the Removal of Methylene Blue by NaOH Treated Waste Writing Papers

Initial concentration Methylene Blue (ppm)	Final concentration (ppm)	Removal percent (%)
20	5.337	73.317
40	15.394	61.514
60	23.558	60.737
80	37.202	53.498
100	51.067	48.933

TWP = NaOH Treated Waste Writing Papers, Dosage = 0.4 g / 50mL

Table (3) Effect of Dosage of Untreated Waste Writing Papers on the Removal of Methylene Blue

Dosage (g)	Final concentration (ppm)	Removal percent (%)
0.2	15.635	21.827
0.4	11.798	41.010
0.6	9.490	52.548
0.8	7.606	61.971
1.0	6.077	69.615

UWP = Untreated Waste Writing Papers, Initial concentration of Methylene Blue= 20ppm

Table (4) Effect of Dosage of NaOH Treated Waste Writing Papers on the Removal of Methylene Blue

Dosage (g)	Final concentration (ppm)	Removal percent (%)
0.2	26.192	34.519
0.4	15.394	61.514
0.6	9.106	77.236
0.8	5.837	85.409
1.0	3.327	91.683

**TWP = NaOH Treated Waste Writing papers,
Initial concentration of Methylene Blue = 40ppm**

Figure (7) Removal percent of methylene blue by UWP as a function of dosage

Figure (8) Removal percent of methylene blue by TWP as a function of dosage

Table (5) Comparison of Removal Percent of Methylene Blue by UWP and TWP

Adsorbent	Removal percent of methylene blue
UWP	41.106
TWP	61.514

Figure (9) Comparison of removal percent of methylene blue by UWP and TWP

UWP= Untreated Waste Writing Papers,
Initial concentration of methylene blue = 20 ppm
TWP= NaOH Treated Waste Writing Papers,
Initial concentration of methylene blue = 40 ppm

Conclusion

Physicochemical properties of untreated waste writing papers (UWP) and NaOH treated waste writing papers (TWP) showed that TWP has higher moisture content, ash content and pH value than UWP. The corresponding functional groups of cellulosic samples were observed from FTIR analysis. The bands around 1650- 1300 cm^{-1} are assigned to ring vibration in a large aromatic skeleton generally found in cellulosic material. From SEM analysis, morphology of UWP showed the small fibrous substances whereas TWP indicated the long fibers with pit structure.

The sorption of methylene blue onto UWP and TWP were studied with various initial concentrations of methylene blue and adsorbent dosage. At optimum contact time of 4h and 0.4 g dosage, although 41.106 % of 20 ppm methylene blue was removed by UWP, 61.514 % of 40 ppm methylene blue was removed by TWP. Therefore, TWP having high specific surface area can be used as effective and efficient adsorbent for the removal of methylene blue.

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